

NON-UNIFORMITY OF THE FILAMENT DISTRIBUTION IN FIBRE BUNDLES AND ITS EFFECT ON DEFECT FORMATION IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOULDING

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1 Motivation

Minimisation of the void content created during impregnation of reinforcement fabrics with liquid resin systems, is critical for the quality of finished polymer composite components, in particular if Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes are employed for manufacture. Different flow velocity of the injected resin in different zones of the reinforcement may result in an uneven flow front and formation of resin-free dry spots. These may result in a reduction in the matrix-dominated mechanical properties, in particular strength in shear, bending and compression, of the finished composite. The main focus of this study is the characterisation of the local distribution of filaments within fibre bundles and the influence of the degree of uniformity on formation of micro-scale voids.

2 Material characterisation

Composite plaques with dimensions 125 mm × 60 mm were made from uni-directional carbon fibre fabric (filament count in fibre bundles $c_f = 12K$) and an epoxy resin system. The plaques were moulded by injecting the liquid resin into a stiff metallic tool containing the fabric. The resin viscosity during injection ($\eta = 0.025 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) was controlled via its temperature. Specimens were moulded at different cavity height, i.e. level of fabric compression, and injection pressure.

Micrographic analysis of the moulded and cured specimens allowed the filament distribution within fibre bundles, which is typically non-uniform, to be identified and micro-scale dry spots to be detected. The results indicate that at given injection pressure, number and size of intra-bundle dry spots increase

with increasing cavity height, i.e. decreasing level of fabric compression (illustrated qualitatively in Fig. 1).

With increasing level of compression, the filament distribution within the fibre bundles tends to become more uniform, which is related to the reduction in inter-filament spacing and increasing packing density. This is illustrated in Fig. 2, where the filament distribution is characterised by the average distances between a filament and its neighbours, which decrease with increasing level of compression. Increasing packing density is equivalent to a more uniform permeability distribution (at the micro-scale) and even flow front propagation, eventually resulting in a low content of entrapped gas bubbles, even if the total bundle permeability is reduced.

The local distribution of V_f , which is correlated to the filament distribution, can be determined by analysis of micrographs (e.g. employing the moving window technique). An example for the distribution is given in Fig. 3.

3 Permeability field

For characterisation of flow within fibre bundles, local permeability values can be calculated by homogenisation of filaments and inter-filament spaces. From the local fibre volume fraction $V_f(x, y)$, the local permeability of the fibre bundle parallel (K_1) and perpendicular (K_2) to its axis can be determined based on the equations derived by Gebart [1],

$$K_1 = \frac{R^2}{4c_1} \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2}, K_2 = c_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{f\max}}{V_f}} - 1 \right)^{5/2} R^2, \quad (1)$$

where c_1 , c_2 and V_{fmax} are geometrical constants. The values of the constants in Eq. (1) depend on the filament packing arrangement, which can be characterised by the number of nearest neighbours of a filament, N_{nn} , i.e. the number of neighbours with (approximately) identical minimum distance. For periodic filament arrangements, c_1 and c_2 can be determined in analogy to the analytical derivation described by Gebart for square ($N_{nn} = 4$) and hexagonal ($N_{nn} = 6$) packing. For triangular ($N_{nn} = 3$) packing, c_1 may be approximated by the value for a circular arrangement, which is 2 based on the values given by Gebart. Considering flow through a unit cell, the value of c_2 can be approximated as 0.69. For a pentagonal ($N_{nn} = 5$) filament arrangement, c_1 and c_2 can be determined from interpolation based on the power law approximations

$$c_1 = 2.63 N_{nn}^{-0.26} \text{ and } c_2 = 3.75 N_{nn}^{-1.57}, \quad (2)$$

which were derived by curve fitting to the constants for three, four and six nearest neighbours. Values for V_{fmax} can be determined analytically based on geometrical considerations. For a number of filament arrangements characterised by N_{nn} , estimated values of c_1 , c_2 and V_{fmax} are listed in Table 1.

The number of nearest neighbours tends to increase with increasing fibre volume fraction, i.e. increasing packing density. A correlation between N_{nn} and V_f can be established based on the probability distributions of V_f at different values of N_{nn} (which were generated assuming V_f to be normally distributed), as shown in Fig. 4. These were determined by identifying zones with defined filament arrangement (characterised by N_{nn}) on micrographs of fibre bundle cross-sections and the local V_f in these zones. From Fig. 4, the value of N_{nn} most probable to be found at a given V_f was determined. The results listed in Table 2 allow N_{nn} to be estimated as a function of V_f .

For a fibre bundle with randomly distributed filaments, Eq. (1) allows the permeability to be approximated locally based on $V_f(x, y)$ and the local values of c_1 , c_2 and V_{fmax} , which are estimated from $N_{nn}(x, y)$. The results plotted in Fig. 5 show that K_1 decreases continuously with increasing V_f . On the other hand, K_2 is a discontinuous function of V_f . The discontinuities are related to changes in filament arrangement with increasing packing density, where

for each type of arrangement, K_2 decreases continuously with increasing V_f . The most significant discontinuity occurs at the transition from triangular to square filament arrangement. This reflects the dimensions of gaps between filaments, which are small for $N_{nn} = 3$, even if V_f is relatively low, and larger for $N_{nn} = 4$ at slightly increased V_f . However, the dependencies of K_1 and K_2 on V_f plotted in Fig. 5 apply locally and do not necessarily imply that a whole bundle, in which local effects are averaged over the bundle dimensions, behaves in the same way.

Based on typical measured dimensions of fibre bundle cross-sections, randomised local values of V_f can be generated, which follow the corresponding experimentally observed distributions (as in Fig. 3) and thus reproduce the non-uniform filament distributions in the actual bundles. For each local value of V_f , K_1 and K_2 can be determined from Fig. 5. Since the difference in inter-filament void sizes (V_f) determines the difference in local flow front propagation in the voids (K_1) and the fluid exchange between voids (K_2) [2], statistical evaluation of the generated local distributions (Fig. 6) and their gradients may give some indication on the probability for dry spot formation or the void content to be expected.

4 Micro-scale flow simulation

Complementing the approach of local homogenisation and permeability calculation described in the previous section, non-uniform filament distributions were modelled in detail to allow 2D flow to be simulated on fibre bundle cross-sections (using the CFD code FLUENT). While the feasibility of this approach has been demonstrated before, e.g. by Cai and Berdichevsky [3], modelling flow through arrays of individual filaments is not practical at the fibre bundle scale with typically several thousand filaments. The filament arrangement in the models was correlated to actual distributions via the measured distances between neighbouring filaments (Fig. 2). The micro-structure was generated following an adjusted version of the procedure described by Vaughan and McCarthy [4]. Here, a pre-determined number of filaments are placed at given distances, which are picked randomly from the measured distributions, and in random directions relative to a randomly placed

starting point. After the last filament is placed, the starting point is set to the first newly placed filament, and the process is repeated. These steps are repeated until the specified domain is filled with filaments, and no additional filament can be placed. Pressure gradients were applied across the models as boundary condition to simulate transverse flow. In the results for steady state (fully saturated) flow, zero flow velocity or zero pressure gradient indicates probable zones for dry spot formation in transient (unsaturated) flow. Results for the local flow velocity field (Fig. 7) indicate that most of the fluid is flowing through a few major flow channels which are formed in between clusters of filaments. Outside of these channels, the flow velocity is very low, suggesting that hardly any fluid will flow into the filament clusters. This implies that the probability for gas entrapment in these zones is high, which may result in void formation in the final part.

The micrographs in Fig. 2b and the reconstructed filament distributions in the models in Fig. 7 also illustrate how local fibre volume fraction and filament arrangement (with different N_{nm} , as characterised in Table 1), vary depending on the position within the bundle cross-section. As suggested by Fig. 5, flow velocity and thus the probability for local filling is not only dependent on the fibre volume fraction, but also on the local filament arrangement.

5 Conclusions

Micrographic analysis of specimens of a UD composite moulded at different compaction levels showed that, with increasing level of compression, the filament distribution within the fibre bundles becomes more uniform, and number and size of intra-bundle dry spots decrease. Based on the observed local fibre volume fractions and filament distributions within fibre bundles, local permeabilities can be estimated. These may give some indication on the probability for dry spot formation or the void content to be expected when the bundles are impregnated with a liquid resin system. In addition, non-uniform filament distributions as in the actual fibre bundles were modelled in detail. Numerical flow simulations on fibre bundle cross-sections indicate that most of the fluid is flowing through a few major flow channels, which may result in void formation in the final part. The local flow velocity field and thus the probability for dry spot formation is not only dependent on the fibre volume fraction, but also on the local filament arrangement.

Future work will deal with more quantitative correlation of the void content with the degree of non-uniformity of the filament distribution in the fibre bundle. Transient filling will also be investigated using CFD.

Fig. 1. Micrographic cross-sections of composite specimens produced by resin injection at a gauge pressure $p = 4$ bar and varying cavity height; dry spots appear black.

Fig.2. a) Distances of a filament to its n th nearest neighbour in μm ; b) filament arrangement at different global fibre volume fractions V_f .

Fig. 3. Histogram of distribution of local V_f in fibre bundle, compressed to 3.6 mm thickness; size of moving window $8.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2$.

Fig. 4. Probability density of fibre volume fraction V_f for filament arrangements with different number of nearest neighbours, N_{nn} .

Fig. 5. Principal permeability values, K_1 and K_2 , as functions of the fibre volume fraction, V_f ; assumption: filament radius $R = 3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$.

Fig. 6. Example for randomised distributions of local V_f and the corresponding K_1 and K_2 for an idealised fibre bundle cross-section at given compression state.

Fig. 7. Velocity distribution (magnitude) for transverse flow (pressure gradient from left to right) through randomised micro-structures; domain size $100 \mu\text{m} \times 100 \mu\text{m}$; top: global $V_f = 0.73$; bottom: global $V_f = 0.67$; light blue: 0 velocity; yellow: max. (arbitrary units); examples for local configurations with N_m as characterised in Table 1 are also highlighted.

Table 1. Parameters c_1 , c_2 and V_{fmax} in Eq. (1) as a function of the number of nearest neighbours, N_{nn} .

N_{nn}	arrangement	c_1	c_2	V_{fmax}
3	triangular	2.00	0.69	0.60
4	square	1.78	0.40	0.79
5	pentagonal	1.72	0.30	0.83
6	hexagonal	1.66	0.23	0.91

Table 2. Most probable number of nearest neighbours, N_{nn} , as a function of the fibre volume fraction V_f .

V_f	N_{nn}
~0.40 .. 0.60	3
0.60 .. 0.73	4
0.73 .. 0.80	5
0.80 .. max	6

References

- [1] B.R. Gebart "Permeability of Unidirectional Reinforcements for RTM". *J Compos Mater*, Vol. 26, No. 8, pp 1100-1133, 1992.
- [2] C. Binetruy, B. Hilaire and J. Pabiot "Tow Impregnation Model and Void Formation Mechanisms during RTM". *J Compos Mater*, Vol. 32, No. 3, pp 223-245, 1998.
- [3] Z. Cai and A.L. Berdichevsky "Numerical Simulation on the Permeability Variations of a Fiber Assembly". *Polym Composite*, Vol. 14, No. 6, pp 529-539, 1993.
- [4] T.J. Vaughan and C.T. McCarthy "A combined experimental-numerical approach for generating statistically equivalent fibre distributions for high strength laminated composite materials". *Compos Sci Technol*, Vol. 70, No. 2, pp 291-297, 2010.